

Impact of Leader's Idealized Influence, Individualized Consideration and Focusing on Effectiveness Behavior on Organizational Performance Mediated by Monetary Reward in Engineering Colleges in Nepal

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Abstract: This paper is the outcome of a research carried out to assess the impact of leader's idealized influence, individualized consideration and focusing on effectiveness (change) on organizational performance, and also the mediation effect of monetary rewards on it in the context of engineering colleges in Nepal. Sample size of 181 was determined using Slovin's formula. A detailed survey preceded by a pilot survey was carried out during the period of August to November, 2024 in the target population of thirty engineering colleges operating in Kathmandu valley, Nepal. Cronbach's alpha's value came out to be .965 giving high reliability to the questionnaire design. Two hundred eighty-five closed questionnaire forms were prepared based on five-point Likert Scale and were administered in-person by the researcher to the senior level employees of administrative and academic faculty departments of those engineering colleges. Two hundred twenty-five responses were received, out of which twenty-four were screened out and the valid two hundred and one questionnaire forms were used for the statistical analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS-27 and PROCESS Macro loaded on SPSS to determine descriptive statistics and inferential statistics such as ANOVA, multiple linear regression, total effect, and direct and indirect effects. The findings show that all the three independent variables have positive, strong and significant impact on organizational performance, giving highest regression coefficient ($\beta=.5901$) to the leader's focusing on effectiveness (change). The findings also show that the indirect effect through the mediator of monetary rewards is insignificant for all variables. The study concludes that the transformational leadership behavior largely has significant impact on organizational performance for its improved and growth of engineering colleges in Nepalese context.

Keywords: *Transformational leadership, idealized influence, individualized consideration, focusing on effectiveness, monetary rewards.*

I. Introduction

Engineering education in Nepal has expanded in the last three decades with the expansion in number of universities and thereby gaining a soaring numbers of engineering colleges. Until 1991, Nepal was grappling with a single university named Tribhuvan University established in 1959, for all types of education. In 1991, a change

in political system took place and the country ushered into a process of democratic transformation. By the end of 2021, number of universities expanded to six and accordingly, the colleges offering engineering education shot up from twenty-nine by almost double to fifty (Giri, et al. (Eds), 2021). The three-year period between 20011 to 2014 was reckoned as a 'boom period' as shown in the Fig. 1 below.

Source: Nepal Engineering Council, Annual Reports, (2008-2021)

Fig. 1: Growth of engineering colleges in Nepal (2008-2021)

The scenario of increasing engineering colleges in the country however was not without a problem, which began to appear as the years passed by. One of the reasons could be attributed to the leadership of those colleges.

Leadership has undergone a continuing evolution of definitions in its concept (Benmira, S., & Agboola, M., 2021). The evolution is so diverse by varieties of ambiguous interpretations that the readers find more and more vagueness in the leadership literature (Van Knippenberg, 2020).

Leaders are perceived as persons possessing the ability to influence the followers and lead the group effectively to bring about the results that are tangible (Johansson, J., & Edwards, M., 2021). Other authors view leadership as the process of influencing the actions of the leader within a group with the consciousness of goal accomplishment in a given circumstance; it is about affecting the subordinates so that they will act with eagerness and excitement towards the attainment of the common goals (Akinbode, G. A., & Fagbohunde, O. B., 2012).

James MacGregor Burns, father of transformational leadership concept, back in 1978 defined the transformational leadership as the process of achieving a common objective through a mutual and coordinated relationship between leader and the followers, which steer them towards a higher level of morale and motivation that brings about the desired change in an organization (Burns, 1978).

Northouse, (2021) elaborates that leadership involves a process in which an individual, the leader, influences a group of people, his subordinates, to achieve shared objectives (Northouse, 2021). Armstrong, (2014) sees it as an act of stimulating the followers to their best to achieve the highly ideal outcome (Armstrong, 2014). It may be concluded that leadership is the art of stirring a group of people from the status quo to move consciously ahead to work together to accomplish the group objectives (Ugochukwu, 2024) for the growth and sustainability of the organization.

II. Problem Statement

Peter Hylton, in an international conference organized in 2011 by American Society of Engineering Education (ASEE) put forward a strong argument asking if the transformational leadership was taught in the engineering education (Hylton, 2011). The question was vital not just for the year 2011 or 2012, but the significance spanned over the whole 21st century. The referred paper apparently may look too delayed literature to be cited in the year 2025, but the theme holds meaning that is impactful for the whole century, the century that belongs to our generation and to the generations that follow. To the researcher, the paper distinctly introduces the gap the engineering education and the engineering institutions are experiencing and putting forward strongly the need to do something academically that contributes to meet the gap. This is as true in Nepal's contemporary engineering educational institutions as was true in American soil some fifteen years ago. Further, Shaflu, et al., (2019) in their paper *The Impact of Leadership on Organizational performance*, find ineffective leadership as one of the notably significant factors for poor delivery of the institutions.

On his blog PRAKASH ANTHRO (2018), Associate Prof. Prakash Upadhyay published an article in which he discusses that the higher education in Nepal is badly affected by politicization and the resulting instable leadership issues and recommends ways out to address them, if not resolve them (Upadhyay, 2018). Another study has highlighted that the extensive studies were carried out in higher educational sector in developed countries whereas very little being done in low income and backward countries (Khanal, J., Gaulee, U., & Simpson, O., 2021) showing the gap why many countries like Nepal fall in the less developed countries.

The emerging practical issue gradually turning to an alarming challenge is illustrated by an article published online on December 17, 2023 (Rai, 2023). The article listed thirteen leading engineering colleges of Nepal showing very poor enrollment status of the prospective students, notably below the intake capacity allotted for those colleges indicating heavy erosion of trust over Nepalese engineering education and institutions. The article presented that, two of those thirteen colleges were in critical stage (more than 75 percent seats remaining vacant), five were in serious stage (45-65 percent seats remaining vacant) and three were in alert stage (22-27 percent seats remaining vacant) with only three in comfortable stage (about 5-14 percent seats remaining vacant). Interpretation of this scenario may differ based on the perspectives related with the position of the person, but a common understanding may be fairly drawn that the engineering educations sector is heading towards a quagmire of problem net, and the ineffective leadership may be one of the causes.

The present study observes the issues through the lens of transformational leadership of the college chief. This paper is an outcome of the study on the impact of the three elements of the transformational leadership, particularly the idealized influence, the individualized consideration and focusing on effectiveness behaviors of the leader, the third one being a new addition (extension) proposed by the study.

III. Hypothesis proposition

Customarily, null hypotheses (H_0) is the statement of 'no effect or impact', meaning the statement implies that any observed impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable is due to a random chance and, not a true causal relationship. It is assumed that this null hypothesis is true as a default. The research is conducted to disprove this assumption, meaning to show with evidence that the null hypothesis is unlikely to be true. Then, it suggests that the observed impact or the relationship is not due to random chance, but is a true causal relationship. The assumed hypotheses are proposed as follow:

For X_1 : Leader's idealized influence behavior

H_0 Leader's idealized influence behavior has no impact on the organizational performance

- For X_2 : Leader's individualized consideration behavior
 H_0 Leader's individualized consideration behavior has no impact on the organizational performance
- For X_3 : Leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior (proposed extension)
 H_0 Leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior has no impact on the organizational performance

The condition is that, if the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is rejected suggesting the proposed hypothesis is not established. Conversely, if the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, in which case, the proposed hypothesis shall be considered established for this research.

IV. Review of literature

Transformational leadership was postulated first by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 while studying American political leaders. Later, the term 'transformational leadership' was expanded by prominent researchers such as Bernard M. Bass in 1985 and other researchers such as Bruce J. Avolio (1995) and Ronald E. Riggio (2005), who restructured the concept for the growth and sustainability of organizations.

Burns (1978) posits that transformational leaders work closely and reciprocate with their followers, inspire and motivate each other, thereby moving ahead together towards shared objectives and attain transformation. His work defines distinction between the management and leadership, elaborates them with clarification that the leadership is more of a combined feature of vision, personality and style of behavior (Burns, 1978).

Expanding the Burns' theory of transformational leadership, Bass makes a notable addition of knowledge by shifting of focus of the theory more towards the followers. His theory posits if the leader can instill a sense of trustworthiness, stimulate a wisdom of loyalty and a sense of respect leading to cause appreciation, the followers will go beyond the early expectation out of them and they will do so with enthusiasm. Their core message on transformational leadership is that the leadership is inspiring and motivating to the followers and both sides work with eagerness and zeal to attain the shared goals beyond expectations (Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J., 1994).

After a rigorous work, Bass came up with his seminal findings of four essential components of transformational leadership behaviors. These behaviors include inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence and individualized consideration. The current paper however covers two of these core elements, namely, the leader's idealized influence and individualized consideration behaviors, and adds a new element 'focusing on effectiveness (change)' behavior as the third element. These three elements are the independent variables (X_i) for the study and the organizational performance is the dependent variable (Y) in the scenario of engineering colleges setting in Nepalese context. A mediating variable, incentive of monetary rewards, is considered as the intermediate variable denoted by $Z_{mediate}$.

Leader's idealized influence behavior

In idealized influence, the transformational leaders exhibit such behaviors that arouse the sense of trust, respect and admiration in the followers and the desires to admire and imitate their leaders (Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J., 1994). By their behavior, followers are inspired to follow the leader, raising themselves the level of standards of their performance at work (Chebon, et al. 2019). Thus the leader's idealized influence behaviors produce a direct and positive impact on individual performance of the individuals (Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J., 1994). Jangadhi et al. (2015) expressed that such leaders demonstrate high ethical standards (Jandaghi, g., Matin, H., & Farjami, A., 2015). Idealized influence requires the leader

to be confident and powerful, and to influence the subordinates with the leader's values and beliefs (Jiang, W., Zhao, X., & Jiongbina, N., 2017).

Idealized influence helps in inspiring and motivating the employees through model role of the leader (Haseeb, A., Suppramaniam, S., & Subramaniam, A., 2021). Ogola et al. (2017b) explains that the employees' performance or the organizational performance increase when leaders demonstrate the example in sharing the vision, goals and fulfillment of commitments together with ethical standards (Ogola, et al. 2017a).

According to Okoli, et al. (2021), idealized influence is the charismatic aspect of transformational leadership, which involves transmitting to the followers an inspiring vision for the future while exhibiting behavior that makes the leaders respectable (Okoli, I. E. N., Nnabuife, E. K., Adani, I. N., & Ugbo, E. I., 2021). An idealized influence leader pronounces a motivating vision and instills a feeling of trust, pride and esteem among followers over the leadership (Le, L. T. K., & Le, P. B., 2021). Followers develop an emotional attachment and strong identity with the leaders when such leaders exhibit behavioral integrity by ensuring that their actions come alike with the reiterated values (Bass, B., & Riggio, R., 2006).

Leaders who are strong in idealized influence are not spontaneous or impulsive, rather they show the behaviors that are more adhered and undeterred to ethical and moral values (Okoli, et al., 2021). Due to such ethical attributes of the leaders, the followers accept them as their worthy role models who inculcate admiration and trust on them (Kitur, K., Choge, J., & Tanui, E., 2020). It may thus be concluded that the influence by such leaders is a product of both their own behavior and the behavior as perceived by their followers (Kariuki, 2021).

Idealized influence leaders are viewed as risk-takers and enthusiasts (Okoli, et al., 2021). They possess the aptitude to explain, to plan, envision, and implement change plan in organization because they are ready to accept the challenges of change and the risks that lie ahead. The enthusiasm exhibited by the leaders inspires their followers to be hopeful of the goal attainment and a better future, thus preparing them to embrace modification instead of staying with no change status. The risk taking trait enables the leaders to adapt with the abnormal circumstances and thereby fostering the organization's resilience capacity needed for its survival and sustenance.

In 2017, Brown and his research team explained the behavior of idealized influence by breaking it into two sub-themes, such as, idealized influence attributed (IIa) and idealized influence behavior (IIb) (Brown, S., Chen, L., & O' Donnell, E., 2017). These two sub-themes are defined to illustrate idealized influence leadership. The first one, idealized influence-attributed (IIa) refers to the perception of the followers over the leader whereas idealized influence-behavior (IIb) refers essentially to the leader's own behaviors (Afshari, 2021). Afshari (2021) has taken this granular aspect into consideration suggesting that the two sub-dimensions are representative in the role the leader and the followers play.

Idealized influence covers and illustrates the emotional attachment aspect of the organizational commitment demonstrated by the leader, which is "the power of individual identification that empowers the identity of the particular organization the leader is involved in" (Wulani, et al., 2019) in (Kariuki, 2021).

Some literature considers the idealized influence and the charismatic behaviors of leadership alike and describes these transformational leaders adopt such manners and behaviors that symbolize them as role models for the followers (Gomes, 2014); (Ngaithe, et al, 2016). Thus, idealized influence behavior is attributed to the leader possessing the traits such as charisma, ethics and the ability to effectively communicate the organization's vision to their followers (Ngaithe, et al, 2016). These leaders exhibit

strong personal ideals and values that set them different from the rest establishing distinctively positive images for the subordinates in the organization (Gomes, 2014).

Leader's individualized consideration behavior

Individualized consideration entails the development of followers through coaching, mentoring and teaching. The individualized consideration leader demonstrates high concern for their followers, treats them as individuals and gets to know well about them and listens to both their concerns and ideas (Chebon, et al. 2019). Individualized consideration refers to the leadership where a leader pays attention to the followers individually identifying their different needs and discovers the areas of motivation to each individual (Avolio, J., & Bass, B., 1995). They argue that paying individualized attention accords leaders to become familiar and move closer with followers, enhance mutual communication and improves interpersonal information exchange, then allows the leaders to choose to support the followers individually.

A satisfied human resource contributes to create a congenial atmosphere within the organization enabling each individual to perform better. A satisfied employee is prepared to put in more effort to performance, and is expected to work harder and better resulting into better performance by the organization (Pushpakumari, 2008). When individualized consideration leaders are sensitive to the individuals and give personal attention, their acts trigger feelings of happiness and comfort among the employees (Ahmad, et al, 2014). Recognition of employees stimulates better productivity. Recognition can be one of the policies an organization can adopt to increase workers' performance and thereby increase the organization's performance in terms of productivity (Meyer, K., & Peng, M., 2006). By being sensitive to the individual's specific, capabilities and personal issues, individualized consideration allows transformational leaders to assign employees tasks and duties they are most competent at doing (Datche, A., & Mukulu, E., 2015).

Individualized consideration leaders can better manage conflicts or neutralize chances of conflict by resolving such conflicts through engagement of the employees making them feel that they are also a part of the solution, thus not allowing a chance to jeopardize the organizational performance or productivity (Awan, A. G., & Anjum, K., 2015).

The mentorship is a strong aspect of individualized consideration dimension of the leadership and is a process of nurturing the individual capacity of the subordinates of an organization (Edirisooriya, 2020). The process of mentorship brings the role modeling function of the leaders' idealized influence behavior (IIb) closer to the followers and makes the leadership more distinctive allowing the followers to learn and develop trust and respect to their role models (Bass, B., & Riggio, R., 2006).

Leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior

Leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior is the third and new independent variable the researcher attempts to study. The research deals with the behavioral effectiveness of the leader to act as independent variable, the predictor, and not the organization's effectiveness or organizational performance, which would then become the dependent variable.

An effective leader is the one who possesses the traits such as being confident, honesty in the behavior and clarity of interest (Joseph, A. A., & Ideraola, A. O., 2021). The leader should therefore focus on those traits while making their role effective in the organization. Successful firms are always attributed to these traits of effective leadership. These leaders besides having abilities to encourage teams in the organization towards better performance, are known to encourage innovations which in turn contributes

to the organizational effectiveness (Karauri, L. G., & Kyongo, J., 2024). Their intent is always focused on effectiveness, beyond the short term target, e.g., annual targets, etc. These leaders are regarded as 'men of vision' and considered source of inspiration and motivation for their followers (Bass, B. M., & Bass, R., 2008) as cited in (Lanston University, 2020). These leaders are termed effective leaders as their personality aura and the traits in combination inspire their followers to achieve ambitious goals (Joseph, A. A., & Ideraola, A. O., 2021).

Leadership's fundamental jurisdiction is to encourage and inspire team work and collaboration for the firm he is engaged in towards higher performance (Alzoraiki, et al. 2018). Besides, such leadership also needs to focus on building a commitment thread among the subordinates binding them towards attainment of higher performance.

Effective leadership depends on the ability of the leader to transfer some authority to subordinates and also to keep them abreast to be a part in the process of decision making framework (Sloof, R., & von Siemens, F. A., 2021). They posit that these leaders delegate a part of their power to the subordinates while carrying out the tasks. Sloof. & von Siemens (2021) further argue that such leaders should act to make sure that the followers have freedom to exercise some kind of control while carrying out their works. Absence of such allowance, their sense of commitment will weaken and the subordinates will show abnormal kinds of behavior during the duty, which in turn results into a poor performance. This suggests that the followers are negatively impacted when the leaders are preoccupied with the pursuit of their self-interest which concur with the findings (Cakir, F. S., & Adiguzel, Z., 2020).

Morford, (1987) proposes that the effective leadership is constituted of at least five themes for which leaders ought to focus on to make their leadership effective and have impact on the organizational performance (Morford, 1987). The first theme *centrality* suggests that an effective leader needs to rise above self-interest and remain adhered to the accepted aligned values. The second theme *visions and objectives* suggests that an effective leader must possess the ability to effectively articulate the visions and objectives they have. The third theme *allowance for conflict* suggests that an effective leader needs to allow a space for consultation, discussion and debate to ensure that the organization is in the path of revisit and growth (Morford, 1987). The fourth theme *leader's personal characteristics* suggests that the effective leaders should be able to differentiate the traits of the followers and of the unsuccessful leaders (Morford, 1987). The fifth theme *the leader's ability to interaction* suggests that the effective leaders needs to remain alert, responsive and accommodative to the prevailing situation and deliver.

Effectiveness of leadership is measured on the basis of whether the results are positive in terms of the objectives (Madanchian, et al., 2017). For example, leadership effectiveness can be measured either through evaluation of results on the specific target items and, or, through the evaluation by the subordinate team members (Madanchian, et al., 2017).

V. Data Collection and Methodology

The primary basis of research design considered for the research is the positivist philosophy. Positivist research philosophy is the fundamental foundation of the research with deductive approach and the research follows quantitative methodology under an explanatory research design. It is cross-sectional study and survey method has been extensively used for data collection. Closed questionnaires, designed on Likert Scale of five points (SD to Neutral to SA) is the instrument used for measurement. The unit of measurement is comprised of the engineering colleges (30 in total) operating within the valley of Kathmandu, the capital of Nepal. Target population is composed of the senior level employees working at different departments in these engineering colleges.

Stratified not-probability convenience sampling technique was used for pilot survey and stratified non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for the final survey. The pilot survey was to test the reliability of the questionnaires from among the target population for which convenience sampling techniques was used. Fifty samples were planned from six colleges two each from the three leading universities. However, sixty-two valid samples were received and analyzed. The final survey was a full scale survey focused exclusively on all the senior level employees working in the engineering colleges aimed at meeting the purpose of the research for which the purposive sampling technique was chosen. Using Slovin formula, the minimum sample size computed 181 against which the research collected 201 valid responses and carried out analysis.

While designing questionnaires, a previously published paper by Jyoti, J., & Bhau, S., (2016) was studied, and elaborated to meet the objectives of the current study (Jyoti, J., & Bhau, S., 2016). Pilot survey was carried out in six engineering colleges representing all the three universities for this purpose. Sixty-two valid samples were analyzed and the Cronbach's Alpha value obtained was .965, which confirmed the reliability of the questionnaire design. This is in line with Zikmund, et al., (2013)'s arguments that Cronbach's alpha close to 1 represents higher reliability and greater internal consistency within the variables.

Final survey was carried out during December 2024 to January, 2025 by administering 285 questionnaire forms to the target population in person by the researcher, of which two hundred and twenty-five (225) responses were collected manually. After screening out 24 responses, the valid responses or the samples for analysis amounted to 201. SPSS-27 developed by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D. was used to determine descriptive and inferential statistics features whereas PROCESS Macro v 4.2 loaded on SPSS-27 was used to determine the total, direct and indirect effects of independent variables on the dependent variable.

VI. Analysis and Results

As a first step, the demographic feature of the respondents taking part in the study is presented. Gender, Age and Profession are the basic parameters used as shown in Table-1 below.

Table – 1 Demographic Setup

	Total	Gender		Age					Profession	
		Female	Male	< 30	30-40	40-50	50-60	> 60	Faculty	Admin
No.	201	28	173	13.1	124.9	47.9	13.1	2	139	62
% age	100	13.9	86.1	6.5	62.2	23.9	6.4	1	69.1	30.9

The table mentions male participation is 86 percent among the total sample of 201, whereas the female participation is quite low, around 14 percent. If we consider the age distribution, the respondents in the 30-40 years range have the remarkable participation (62 percent) followed by the age range of 40-50 years (24 percent). The table also shows that participants of the age younger than 30 years and senior than 50 years are among the lowest and at around the similar @ 6.5 percent. Considering by profession, participants from the academic faculty department seems to be overwhelming (69 percent) compared to those from the administrative departments (around 31 percent).

Next step is to determine descriptive statistics values of the independent variables. The table-2 below presents the descriptive statistics obtained in the study. The table also includes the residual autocorrelation Durbin-Watson (DW) values.

Table – 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variable (X_i)	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard. Deviation	DW
Idealized influence	201	1.40	5.00	4.1239	.61043	1.589
Individualized consideration	201	1.40	5.00	4.0274	.64560	1.432
Focusing on effectiveness	201	1,30	5.00	4.1557	.62014	1.608

The table above shows number of respondents on each of the independent variables, $N=201$, minimum value of the response on Likert scale= 1.40 for each of the 1st and 2nd, and $=1.30$ for the 3rd variable, and the maximum value of the response on Likert sale= 5.0 for each. The values of mean show little more than 4.0 , suggesting that the majority of the responses are leaning from 4.00 (Agree) towards 5.00 (Strongly agree). The standard deviation values show that the pattern of individual members spread around the mean is more than half way but with comfortably closeness. The DW values vary from 1.4 to 1.6 .

Simple Linear Regression Test Results

The tabke-3 below presents the results of simple linear regression test performed using SPSS-27. The table presents inferential statistics parameters including correlation (R and R^2), ANOVA (F-test with significance level) and regression coefficients (α and β with p-values). The values are given in the Table-3 below.

Table – 3 Simple Linear Regression

Variable (X_i)	Correlation		ANOVA		Regression Coefficient			
	R	R^2	F	Sig.	α	β	T	P
Idealized influence	.507	.257	68.826	.000	1.634	.529	8.296	.000
Individualized consideration	.561	.315	91.300	.000	1.587	.554	9.555	.000
Focusing on effectiveness	.574	.329	97.767	.000	1.365	.590	9.888	.000

Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Multiple linear regression test is an advanced analysis which is performed to determine triangular relationship among the independent variable (X_i), dependent variable (Y_{mean}) and the intermediate variable, which is mediating variable ($Z_{mediate}$) for the research. The mediating variable in between the independent and dependent variable shows its mediating effect in the process and helps the researcher to find direct impact and indirect impact.

The test is performed using SPSS-27 and the inferential statistics parameters such as correlation (R and R^2), ANOVA (F-test with significance level) and regression coefficients (α and β with p-values) are determined.

The results are obtained by defining the paths from X_i to $Z_{mediate}$, X_i to Y_{mean} and from $Z_{mediate}$ to Y_{mean} as described under the subtopic Simple Mediation Model and the Fig. 2 below. The results are presented in the Table 4, 5 and 6 under succeeding paragraphs.

Simple Mediation Model

Fig. 2 below presents a simple mediation model which explains the multiple linear regression assessment process. The figure with a vector triangle is self-explanatory.

It shows 'c'-path as direct impact line of X_i on Y_{mean} , 'a'-path as direct impact line of X_i on the mediating variable $Z_{mediate}$ and 'b'-path as also the direct impact line of $Z_{mediate}$ on Y_{mean} . The indirect impact or effect of X_i on Y_{mean} is given by the product of the values of 'a'-path and 'b' path ('a' x 'b'). Thus the total path 'c'-path will be the summation of the values of 'c'-path and 'a' x 'b'- paths.

Fig. 2: Simple Mediation Model

Model

Regression of X_i on $Z_{mediate}$: The 'a'- path

The multiple regression in this research is a three level actions. First, we will see how the independent variables (X_i) regress on the mediating variable ($Z_{mediate}$) depicted by 'a'- path. Table-4 below presents the feature of parameters, the regression and their significance.

Table – 4 Regression of X on $Z_{mediate}$ ('a' path)

Variables (X_i)	Correlation		ANOVA		Regression Coefficients			
	R	R ²	F	Sig.	α	β	t	p
Idealized influence	.3003	.0903	19.7506	.0000	2.4360	.3422	4.4442	.0000
Individualized consideration	.3477	.1209	27.3647	.0000	2.3394	.3744	5.2311	.0000
Focusing on effectiveness	.2797	.0783	16.8948	.0000	2.5440	.3136	4.1103	.0001

Regression of X_i on Y_{mean} : The 'c'- path

Secondly, we see how the independent variables (X_i) regress on the dependent variable (y_{mean}) depicted by 'c'- path. Table-5 below presents the feature of parameters, the regression and their significance.

Table – 5 Regression of X on Y_{mean} ('c'- path)

Variables	Correlation		ANOVA		Regression Coefficients			
	R	R ²	F	Sig.	A	β	T	p
Idealized influence	.5236	.2742	37.3940	.0000	1.6341	.5294	8.2961	.0000
Individualized consideration	.5676	.3222	47.0647	.0000	1.5871	.5538	9.5551	.0000
Focusing on effectiveness	.5867	.3442	51.9689	.0000	1.3653	.5901	9.8877	.0000

Regression of X_i on Y_{mean} through $Z_{mediate}$: The 'a' and 'b'- path

Thirdly, we see how the independent variables (X_i) regress on the dependent variable (Y_{mean}) through the mediating variable ($Z_{mediate}$) depicted by 'c'- and 'b'- paths. Table-6 below presents the feature of parameters, the regression and their significance.

Table – 6 Regression of X on Y_{mean} through $Z_{mediate}$ ('c' and 'b' path)

Variables	α	β_1	β_2	t_1	t_2	p_1	p_2	(LLCI) ₂	(ULCI) ₂
Idealized influence	1.3271	.4863	.1260	7.3352	2.1650	.0000	.0316	.0112	.2408
Individualized consideration	1.3861	.5216	.0859	8.4651	1.5013	.0000	.1349	-.0269	.1988
Focusing on effectiveness	1.0697	.5536	.1162	8.9840	2.1137	.0000	.0358	.0078	.2246

The multiple linear regression gives regression models as:

$$Y_{mean} = \alpha + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Z_{mediate}, \text{ thus,}$$

For idealized influence behavior,

$$Y_{mean} = 1.3271 + .4863X + .1260 Z_{mediate}$$

For individualized behavior,

$$Y_{mean} = 1.3861 + .5216X + .0859 Z_{mediate}$$

For focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior,

$$Y_{mean} = 1.0697 + .5536X + .1162 Z_{mediate}$$

The Mediation Effect

Evaluation of mediation effect is explained by determining three effects of the independent variables: the total effect, direct effect and the indirect effect, on the dependent variable using the analysis technique of PROCESS Macro v. 4.2 loaded on SPSS. In this analysis, the indirect effect is the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable through the mediating variable (M: $Z_{mediate}$), also called mediated by the intermediate variable.

The Total Effect

The total effect is the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable in the absence of the mediating variable (c-path). These effects and their amounts with their statistical significance status are presented in the table -7 below.

Table – 7 Total Effect of X_i on Y_{mean} ('c' - path)

Variables	Effect Amount	t- value	p- value	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Idealized influence behavior	.5294	8.2961	.0000	.4036	.6553
Individualized consideration behavior	.5538	9.5551	.0000	.4395	.6681
Focusing on effectiveness behavior	.5901	9.8877	.0000	.4724	.7077

The table shows that the total effect value is the highest for the third variable leader's 'focusing on effectiveness' behavior (.5901) followed by the second variable 'individualized consideration' (.5538) and then by the first variable 'idealized influence' behavior (.5294). It is explained from values that all the total effects are statistically significant and none of the boot strapped confidence intervals include zero.

The Direct Effect

The direct effect refers to the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable with the presence of the mediating variable (c' -path). These effects and their amounts with their statistical significance are given in the Table -8 below.

Table – 8 Direct Effect of X_i on Y_{mean} ('c' - path)

Variables	Effect Amount	t- value	p- value	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Idealized influence behavior	.4863	7.3352	.0000	.3556	.6170
Individualized consideration behavior	.5216	8.4651	.0000	.4001	.6431
Focusing on effectiveness behavior	.5536	8.9840	.0000	.4321	.6751

The table shows that the direct effect value is the highest for the third variable, leader’s ‘focusing on effectiveness’ behavior (.5536) followed by the second variable ‘individualized consideration’ (.5216) and then by the first variable ‘idealized influence’ behavior (.4863). The table also shows that all the direct effects are statistically significant ($p < .05$) and none of the boot strapped confidence intervals include zero.

The Indirect Effect

The indirect effect also called the mediation effect refers to the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the mediating variable, that is, taking into account the mediating effect of the intermediate variable (‘a’ * ‘b’ –path). These effects and their amounts with their statistical significance status are presented in the Table -9 below.

Table – 9 Indirect Effect of X_i on Y_{mean} through $Z_{mediate}$ (a*b)

Variables	Effect Amount	Boot SE	Explanation a * b	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Idealized influence behavior	.0431	.0258	.3422 * .1260	-.0022	.1001
Individualized consideration behavior	.0322	.0260	.3744 * .0859	-.0192	.0844
Focusing on effectiveness behavior	.0364	.0238	.3136 * .1162	-.0042	.0891

The table shows that the indirect effect is weak in general. The table also shows that the indirect effect value is the highest for the first variable, leader’s ‘idealized influence’ behavior (.0431) followed by the third variable, ‘focusing on effectiveness’ (.0364) and then followed by the second variable, ‘individualized consideration’ behavior (.0322). In contrary to the other effects, the table also shows that all the indirect effects are statistically insignificant as their boot strapped confidence intervals include zero.

VII. Findings and Discussion

The preliminary findings show that the group test (F –test) values are significant for all the independent variables indicating a positive relationship and suggesting that the researcher can now advance forward to perform individual t- tests. The significant results of the F- test also suggest that the proposed null hypothesis that ‘the independent variables have no impact on the dependent variable’ is rejected for all the three cases. This affirms that the conditions for the alternate hypothesis are satisfied suggesting that the direct and positive impact of independent variables on the dependent variable is confirmed and established for the research.

Findings based on the statistical and inferential tests are discussed in the subsequent paragraphs.

Impact of the leader’s idealized influence

The idealized influence behavior’s overall mean value from the descriptive statistics Table-2 stands at 4.1239 indicating the sample responses to the questionnaires for this leadership behavior have a general trend to lean towards ‘strongly agree’ from ‘agree’ on Likert’s scale. This suggests that the respondents in the engineering colleges seem to ‘more than agree’ in general and that the leader’s idealized influence behavior have a positive impact on the college’s organizational performance. The standard deviation value of .61043 suggests that the items within the independent variable are largely closely spread around the mean. The same table shows the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.589 (<2) depicting a positive autocorrelation in the residuals.

Table-3 presents the results of simple linear regression test, which affirms that the relationship between the leader’s idealized influence behavior with organizational performance is positive and strong. It suggests each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 52.9 percent.

Table- 4, 5 and 6 present the results of multiple linear regression test. Table- 4 shows regression on the intermediate variable (Z_{mediate}) ('a'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, moderately strong ($\beta=.3422$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the intermediate variable by 34.22 percent. Table- 5 shows regression on the predictor variable (Y_{mean}) ('c'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, fairly strong ($\beta=.5294$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 52.94 percent. The Table-6 presents the 2- stage multiple linear regression results on Y_{mean} , one due to the independent variable (X_1) and the other due to the mediating variable (Z_{mediate}). The two regression models give the regressions values $\beta_1=.4863$ ('c'- path) and $\beta_2=.1260$ ('b'- path) respectively suggesting moderately strong regression of independent variable (X_1) and fairly weak regression (β_2) of mediator (Z_{mediate}) on predicting variable (Y_{mean}).

Total Effect, Direct Effect and Indirect Effect

Table-7 shows the results of the total effect (c- path) of leader's idealized influence behavior (.5294), on organizational performance, which may be considered as strong and significant ($t=8.2961$, $p=.000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limits (.4036, .6553), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-8 presents the outputs of the direct effect (c'- path) of the behavior (.4863), which may be considered as fairly strong and significant ($t=7.3352$, $p=.000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limits (.3556, .6170), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-9 shows the results of the indirect effect (a*b - path) of the leader's behaviors. Indirect effect is the leader behavior (X_1)'s mediated effect through the mediating variable on the organizational performance. Its significance was tested by PROCESS Macro determining the position of its confidence level within the range of bootstrapped confidence levels. In this case, the indirect effect value stands at .0431, which is very weak, though strongest among the three variables. The confidence level value seems to navigate within a range between negative lower and positive upper limits of bootstrapped confidence level (-.0022, .1001) suggesting that the bootstrapped values include zero, and therefore the relationship or the indirect effect is statistically insignificant.

Impact of leader's individualized consideration

The individualized consideration behavior's overall mean value from the descriptive statistics Table-2 stands at 4.0274 indicating the sample responses to the questionnaires for this leadership behavior have a general trend to lean towards 'strongly agree' from 'agree' on Likert's scale, though marginally. This suggests that the respondents in the engineering colleges seem to 'more than agree' or 'agree' in general that the leader's individualized consideration behavior has a positive impact on the college's organizational performance. The standard deviation value stands at .64560, and is the highest among the three variables, suggesting that the items within the independent variables are largely closely spread around the mean, a bit more spread than for the other two variables. The same table shows the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.432 depicting a positive autocorrelation in the residuals (<2) which indicates less positive than the other two variables, but still shows a positive correlation.

The simple linear regression test results, Table-3 shows correlation direction ($R=.561$) and correlation strength ($R^2=.315$) indicating positive and fairly strong. The group test value ($F=91.300$, $\text{Sig}=.000$) is notably strong and significant, which suggest that the null hypothesis is rejected. The regression

coefficient ($\beta=.554$) of the independent variable is pretty strong and also significant ($t=9.555$, $p=.000$), which suggests that each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 55.4 percent.

Table- 4, 5 and 6 present the results of multiple linear regression test. Table- 4 shows regression on the intermediate variable (Z_{mediate}) ('a'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, moderately strong ($\beta=.3744$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the intermediate variable by 37.44 percent. Table- 5 shows regression on the predictor variable (Y_{mean}) ('c'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, notably strong ($\beta=.5538$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 55.38 percent. The Table-6 presents the 2- stage multiple linear regression results on dependent variable Y_{mean} , one due to the independent variable (X_2) and, the other, due to the mediating variable (Z_{mediate}). The 2- stage regression models give the regressions values $\beta_1=.5216$ ('c'- path) and $\beta_2=.0859$ ('b'- path) respectively suggesting moderately strong regression of independent variable (X_2) but very weak and statistically insignificant regression (β_2) of mediator (Z_{mediate}) on predicting variable (Y_{mean}).

Total Effect, Direct Effect and Indirect Effect

Table-7 shows the results of the total effect (c-path) of leader's individualized consideration behavior (.55380, which may be considered as 'strong', stronger than the first variable and significant ($t=9.5551$, $p=.0000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limits (.4395, .6681), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-8 presents the outputs of the direct effect (c' - path) of the behavior (.5216), which may be considered as 'strong', stronger than the first variable and significant ($t=8.4651$, $p=.0000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limits (.4001, .6431), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-9 shows the results of the indirect effect (a*b - path) of the leader's behaviors. Indirect effect is the leader behavior (X_i)'s mediated effect through the mediating variable on the organizational performance. Its significance was tested by PROCESS Macro determining the position of its confidence level within the range of bootstrapped confidence levels. In this case, the indirect effect value stands at .0322, which is very weak, weakest among the three combinations. The confidence level value seems to navigate in between the range from negative lower and positive upper limits of bootstrapped confidence level -.0192, .0844) indicating that the bootstrapped values include zero, and suggesting the relationship or the indirect effect is statistically insignificant.

Impact of leader's focusing on effectiveness (change)

The leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior's overall mean value from the descriptive statistics Table-2 stands at 4.1557 indicating the sample responses to the questionnaires in general for this leadership behavior have a general trend to lean towards 'strongly agree' from 'agree' on Likert's scale. This suggests that the respondents in the engineering colleges seem to 'more than agree' in general and that the leader's idealized influence behavior have a positive impact on the college's organizational performance. The standard deviation value of .62014 suggests that the items within the independent variable are largely closely spread around the mean. The same table shows the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.608 depicting a positive autocorrelation in the residuals (<2) which indicates a positive correlation.

The simple linear regression test results, Table-3 shows correlation direction ($R=.574$) and correlation strength ($R^2=.329$) indicating positive direction and fairly strong, strongest among the three variables. The group test value ($F=97.767$, $\text{Sig}=.000$) is remarkably strong and significant, which suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. The regression coefficient ($\beta=.590$) of the independent variable is remarkably strong, strongest among the three variables, and also significant ($t=9.888$, $p=.000$), which suggests that each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 59.0 percent.

Table- 4, 5 and 6 present the results of multiple linear regression test. Table- 4 shows regression on the intermediate variable (Z_{mediate}) ('a'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, poorly strong ($\beta=.3136$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the intermediate variable by 31.36 percent. Table- 5 shows regression on the predicting variable (Y_{mean}) ('c'- path), which affirms that the relationship between the two variables is positive, remarkably strong ($\beta=.5901$) and significant suggesting each unit change in independent variable will impact a change in the dependent variable by 59.01 percent. The Table-6 presents 2- stage multiple linear regression results, one due to the independent variable (X_3) and, the other, due to the mediating variable (Z_{mediate}) on dependent variable (Y_{mean}). The two stage regression model gives the regressions values $\beta_1=.5536$ ('c'- path) and $\beta_2=.1162$ ('b'- path) respectively suggesting a very strong regression (β_1) of independent variable (X_3) and relatively weak regression (β_2) of mediator (Z_{mediate}) on the predicting variable (Y_{mean}).

Total Effect, Direct Effect and Indirect Effect

Table-7 shows the results of the total effect (c- path) of leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior (.5901), which may be considered as 'very strong' and significant ($t=9.8877$, $p=.0000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limits (.4724, .7077), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-8 presents the outputs of the direct effect (c' - path) of the behavior (.5536), which stands out as 'strong', strongest among the three, and significant ($t=8.9840$, $p=.0000$). Its bootstrapped values of confidence level vary in the positive range between the lower and upper limit (.4321, .6751), and therefore do not include zero reaffirming that the relationship is statistically significant.

Table-9 shows the results of the indirect effect (a*b - path) of the leader's behaviors. Indirect effect is the leader behavior (X_i)'s mediated effect through the mediating variable on the organizational performance. Its significance was tested by PROCESS Macro determining the position of its confidence level within the range of bootstrapped confidence levels. In this case the indirect effect value stands at .0364, which is very weak, moderate between the other two. The confidence interval level value seems to navigate in between the range from negative lower and positive upper limits of bootstrapped confidence level (-.0042, .0891) suggesting that the bootstrapped values include zero, and therefore the relationship or the indirect effect is statistically insignificant.

VIII. Conclusion

The output results conclude that in the context of Nepalese engineering colleges, the three independent variables (X_i) have in general direct, strong and significant impact on the organizational performance of those colleges. The simple linear regression analysis shows that the third variable, focusing on effectiveness' has the strongest impact on the dependent variable followed by the second and the first variable. The total effect and the direct effect of the independent variables show the similar trend and rankings.

The indirect effects on the dependent variable from all the three independent variables through the mediating variable of monetary rewards are found weak and statistically insignificant in all the three cases. The results suggest that use of monetary rewards as a means to motivate the senior level staff may not align well with the transformational leadership behaviors of the leader in engineering college setting in the Nepalese context.

The multiple linear regression presents that the regression of independent variables on the intermediate variable (Z_{mediate}) indicates different ranking positions. The second independent variable, individualized consideration, has the strongest impact on the mediator followed by the first and then the third variable respectively. The regression of mediating variable on the dependent variable shows even more interesting feature. The impact of the mediating variable on the dependent variable is the strongest with the first variable, individualized influence, followed by the third and then the second variable, the relationship for the second variable, individualized consideration, being statistically insignificant. Finally, among the mediated regressions on Y_{mean} , value of β_1 is highest for the third, followed by the second and first variables, and the value of β_2 is highest for the first followed by the third and then the second variables.

The research findings are found to concur with previous research findings.

The regression results obtained in the research are compared with the results of the past studies in the similar areas and seen if they concur each other. For leader's idealized influence behavior, Mgqibi & Sines (2020) in their research to assess relationship between idealized influence and the success of change initiative (organizational outcomes) in the U.S. context, found that the relationship between the two variables was a direct and positive. Similarly, in Vietnamese context, the study carried out by Kitur, et al. (2020) to establish relationship between idealized influence and the secondary students' performance revealed a positive and significant relationship between the two.

The results of leader's idealized influence behavior on organizational performance concur with those of (Bandura, 1986), (Ngaithe et al., 2016), (Epitropaki et al., 2017) and (Chebon et al., 2019). Gomes (2014) argues that the leaders with idealized influence behavior inspire employees and protégés to learn and grow advancing them to develop self-identity, self-confidence and well-being.

The results of leader's individualized consideration behavior on organizational performance concur with those of (Axmith, 2005), (Crompton, 2012), and (Chebon et al., 2019), who observe coaching as a necessary practice used by organizations to assist the newly-appointed employees helping them to make successful transition into a role. The research by (Chebon et al., 2019) established link between mentorship and employees' level of confidence, and identified that mentorship as an assist work to the employees, is a non-direct but a significant influence on firm performance and growth. The results also correspond to those of (Gomes, 2014) and (Long et al., 2014), who state that by individualized consideration behavior, the leader may show respect and celebrate the individual contribution that each follower makes to the team.

The results of impact of leader's focusing on effectiveness (change) behavior on organizational performance concur with the findings of Cakir, & Adiguzel, (2020), who studied the relationship between variables such as leadership effectiveness, knowledge sharing behavior, business performance, etc. and found that leadership effectiveness and knowledge sharing, both have direct impact on employee performance. Their findings also revealed that an effective leader focusses on public interest (not self-interest) leading to gaining more trust and subsequent increase in employee retention, consequently enhancing the organizational performance. Cakir, & Adiguzel, (2020) also found that the personal gesture, conduct and cultural tones have a role to play in regards to the effectiveness of leadership.

The findings of this research concur also with the findings of a research conducted by Alzoraiki, et al (2018) in Yemen that demonstrated transformational leadership has a positive relationship with productivity and

performance of the teachers (Alzoraiki, et al., 2018). Effectiveness of leadership or leader's focusing on effectiveness is directly connected with the success rates in case new products are introduced in the market (Hamel, 2006) as cited in (Cakir, F. S., & Adiguzel, Z., 2020). While determining effectiveness of the leader's behavior, one way could be through assessing the views of the dissatisfied employees an organization.

Finally, various articles reviewed by Karauri, & Kyongo, (2004) revealed that effective leadership has an impact on the organizational performance. The transformational leadership to become effective needs to take into consideration the cultural context of the organization while focusing on effectiveness of leadership (Harms, P.D., Han, G., & Chan, K., 2012).

The results of the intermediate variable, monetary reward's mediating effect show that the effects are not significant and may be explained as below.

The overall results of indirect effect of the independent variables through the mediating variable of monetary rewards reveal that the mediation effect of the incentive is weak and insignificant in the context of Nepalese engineering colleges which is confirmed by the bootstrapped values of confidence intervals as they navigate from negative to the positive indicating that the values include zero (Table-9). It implies that adopting such monetary incentive to the senior staff may not work positively and significantly for these three transformational leadership styles in the context of Nepalese engineering colleges setting.

IX. Research contributions

It is important to note that transformational leadership, first conceptualized by Burns in 1978 and later theorized and expanded by Bass in 1985, embodies fundamentally four elements, namely inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence and individualized consideration. In this paper the researcher considers two of the elements, namely, leader's idealized influence and individualized consideration behaviors as independent variables, and proposed to include leader's 'focusing on effectiveness (change)' behavior as the third independent variable in the research.

After data collection and upon the regression analyses, the results show that the third and the new independent variable, may also be included as a new element along with the established two components of transformational leadership behaviors. Statistically, the research results show that the new leadership behavior is found to give the highest positive and significant direct and total effect ($\beta=.5536$ & $.5901$ respectively). Its effect on the intermediate variable of monetary reward (Z_{mediate}) and its mediating effect over the organizational performance through the mediator, are also found positive and significant ($\beta=.3136$ & $.1162$ respectively). These findings effectively suggest to accept the new addition as a significant step forward towards enriching the existing body of knowledge in the area of transformational leadership arena.

The researcher found no difficulty to find literature in the area of leadership and transformational leadership. There is a world full of journal articles, research works and publications from various academic institutions across the globe. However, the researcher had to go through a real hard time in finding literature on transformational leadership in Nepalese context and in higher education sector. It was the hardest experience for engineering education related literature as the literature regarding transformational leadership in engineering institutions was almost nonexistent. So, this research work may be a notable contribution to refer as well as get inspiration for the engineering education industry to think, research and write more thoughtfully in future.

It is believed that the results and findings would provide a significant contribution in policy framing for the better organizational performance, effectiveness, growth and sustainability of the engineering institutions in Nepal.

The exhaustive data collected from two hundred and one samples of the thirty engineering colleges and the rigorous work that followed in this research for the selected leader's three behaviors of transformational leadership

and the valuable findings by using one of the most advanced and widely acclaimed statistical tools of SPSS-27 and PROCESS Macro v. 4.2 may be treasured as a wealth of information for the further research in the sector.

Limitations

This study was carried out collecting data using stratified purposive sampling from all the engineering colleges operating in Kathmandu valley. This methodology however may not have offered space to collect views of other engineering institutions operating outside Kathmandu valley and across Nepal.

The cross-sectional survey gives a full picture of the target population but that total picture is for one point of time only. A research with time series data of say at least five years may provide more holistic and more practicable data and analysis,

Transformational leadership to the discussants may appear to be beautiful topic to talk, discuss and brainstorm. However, to a researcher, the topic of transformational leadership annexed with a term 'behavior' seems to face not joy and enthusiasm, but suspicion and skepticism as the questionnaires laid out before the respondents require them to think about their Principal's day-to-day behavior and give score as their response. At the particular time, probably the respondents feel some kind of bias as they may be considering more as evaluating their own boss rather than giving their candid views as respondents for the academic research.

The overwhelming representation of makes (86 percent) and over-representation of academic faculty (69 percent) (Table 1: Demographic Profile) may have limited the researcher's plan to involve more or less balanced respondents for the research work. This however could be attributed to the real situation of the organizations.

Recommendations

A research carried out at a point of time is never perfect and sufficient, it requires continuous process to get to the goal. Recommendations are therefore vital prescriptions to fulfill the remaining partial aspects not yet given due concern.

Further research and validation is required to accept the leader's 'focusing on effectiveness' behavior as an integral element of transformational leadership. It is gratifying to comment and recommend that this behavior of leadership seems to have established the strongest and significant relationship with performance in the Nepalese engineering colleges.

Leaders of engineering colleges are advised to pay more attention to adopt individual consideration style of transformational leadership while discharging their behavioral duties.

Further research may be prescribed with mediators such as engagement, trust, ethics or knowledge management, etc. that has similar alignment with transformational leadership vibe.

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